

ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER AND GDP IN THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

RUSTAMOVA L.A.

Associate Professor of the Department of Mathematical Economics, Faculty of International Relations and Economics, Baku State University, Baku, Azerbaijan

ALIYEVA R. E.

Master's student, Department of Mathematical Economics, Faculty of International Relations and Economics, Baku State University, Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract: *The article examines the relationship between foreign trade indicators and gross domestic product and evaluates its impact on economic growth. It analyzes the expansion of foreign economic relations in the Republic of Azerbaijan in recent decades, particularly the influence of energy exports on foreign trade turnover and GDP dynamics. At the same time, considering the development of the non-oil sector, export diversification, and structural changes in import-export operations, the impact of foreign trade on economic growth is comprehensively investigated.*

The study employs econometric methods, and the analyses were conducted using the EViews 12 software package. Within this framework, regression and correlation analyses, graphical representations, descriptive statistical calculations, the Dickey–Fuller unit root test, Granger causality test, CUSUM stability test, and cointegration analysis were carried out.

Keywords: *import-export, foreign trade, GDP, econometric analysis, Dickey-Fuller test, the Granger test, and cointegration.*

The primary objective of this article is to study the relationship between foreign trade turnover and gross domestic product in the Republic of Azerbaijan using econometric methods. The study covers the period from 2005 to 2024. The data used in the study were obtained from official statistical sources, and modern time series analysis methods were applied.

The obtained results provide a better understanding of the impact of foreign trade on GDP in the Azerbaijani economy and have practical implications.

The study utilized two main variables. Foreign trade turnover expresses the total volume of foreign trade transactions and was designated as the dependent variable in the analysis. Gross domestic product reflects the total value added created in the country's economy and was included in the model as an independent variable. Both variables are expressed in US dollars.

The primary objective of this article is to construct and analyze an econometric model of the relationship between foreign trade turnover and GDP in the Republic of Azerbaijan. For this purpose, all statistical data on foreign trade turnover and gross domestic product were obtained from official sources, such as the State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan (SSCO) [12]. Annual data for the period from 2005 to 2024 were used.

During the time series analysis, natural logarithms were transformed into natural logarithms, and the relationships between variables were examined to visualize these relationships. This created the conditions for a clearer understanding of the relationships between the given indicators.

The relationship between foreign trade, macroeconomic stability, and economic growth has been widely examined in both theoretical and empirical literature. Early methodological foundations were established by the works cited in [3], which introduced causality testing, in [4], which developed unit root testing procedures, and in [2], which proposed cointegration analysis for identifying long-run equilibrium relationships among time-series variables. These approaches remain essential for analyzing interactions between GDP, trade indicators, money supply, and price dynamics.

Subsequent methodological contributions, including time-series analysis and model-building techniques, expanded the practical application of econometric tools in macroeconomic research. Studies in [5] and [6] emphasize the importance of unit root testing and model specification, while

[7] highlights the role of vector autoregression and error-correction models implemented in econometric software.

Empirical studies focusing on Azerbaijan demonstrate the relevance of these methods for analyzing national economic processes. Research in [1], [8], [9], and [10] investigates cointegration relationships among GDP, trade turnover, money aggregates, consumer prices, and import-export operations.

As a result of the econometric assessment, the following model was constructed to estimate the relationship between gross domestic product (GDP) and foreign trade turnover:

$$\text{LNGDP} = 0.784236875949 \cdot \text{LNFT} + 1.25394205375$$

To ensure stable variance in the time series data and to estimate elasticities between the variables, logarithmic forms of the variables were used. For this purpose, the logarithms of foreign trade turnover and gross domestic product were found and calculated, and the variables used in the model were designated as LNGDP and LNFT, respectively.

Dependent Variable: LNGDP				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 02/20/26 Time: 20:35				
Sample: 1 20				
Included observations: 20				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNFT	0.784237	0.087693	8.942977	0.0000
C	1.253942	0.296914	4.223254	0.0005
R-squared	0.816283	Mean dependent var	3.879423	
Adjusted R-squared	0.806077	S.D. dependent var	0.450570	
S.E. of regression	0.198416	Akaike info criterion	-0.302260	
Sum squared resid	0.708642	Schwarz criterion	-0.202687	
Log likelihood	5.022600	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-0.282822	
F-statistic	79.97684	Durbin-Watson stat	2.067180	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

According to our model, a 1% increase in foreign trade turnover leads to an increase in GDP of approximately 0.78%. The coefficient is statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

The model's free limit is 1.254, which is considered statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.816 confirms the model's high explanatory power. That is, 81.6% of GDP changes are explained by foreign trade turnover. The F-statistic's probability value is 0.000, indicating the statistical significance of the model. The Durbin-Watson statistic was 2.06, indicating the absence of significant autocorrelation issues in the model.

Figure 1. GDP growth dynamics graph dynamics

Graph of foreign trade growth dynamics

As the graphs show, a general upward trend was observed between 2005 and 2014. Although there was a relative decline in 2015–2016, GDP returned to a growth trajectory in subsequent years. In 2020, global economic instability caused by the COVID-19 pandemic led to a decline in both foreign trade turnover and the gross domestic product of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Restrictions on international trade during the pandemic had a negative impact on foreign trade turnover, which also

affected GDP growth. In subsequent years, a gradual recovery in economic activity led to an upward trend in both indicators. In particular, the acceleration of growth in 2021–2023 can be attributed to the recovery of economic activity and foreign economic relations. Overall, both indicators followed a similar trajectory over the long term, resulting in parallel growth during years when economic activity increased.

The **Table 1**.below presents the main descriptive statistics for the foreign trade turnover (LNFT) and the LNGDP on a logarithmic scale.

	LNFT	LNGDP
Mean	3.347816	3.879423
Median	3.478703	3.928579
Maximum	4.029130	4.365897
Minimum	2.146913	2.583243
Std. Dev.	0.519081	0.450570
Skewness	-0.844160	-1.378791
Kurtosis	2.994024	4.773313
Jarque-Bera	2.375384	8.957418
Probability	0.304924	0.011348
Sum	66.95631	77.58845
Sum Sq. Dev.	5.119460	3.857250

Let's examine the correlation dependence between the variables. The results of the analysis show that there is a high and positive correlation between LNFT and LNGDP at the level of 0.90. The correlation coefficient is close to 1. This indicates a strong linear relationship between foreign trade turnover and gross domestic product.

The Dickey-Fuller test is used to test the stationarity of time series. The results of the ADF test for GDP show that the logarithmic gross domestic product indicator was stationary from the first order. According to the results of the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, the logarithmic GDP indicator was not stationary at the LNGDP level, but became stationary after taking its first difference.

Thus, the ADF test statistic for D(LNGDP) was -3.213 , which is less than the critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. Since the p-value is 0.0031, the null hypothesis (the existence of a unit root) is rejected.

This also shows that the GDP variable is integrated from the first order, i.e.:

$$\text{LNGDP} \sim I(1)$$

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.213061	0.0031
Test critical values:		
1% level	-2.708094	
5% level	-1.962813	
10% level	-1.606129	

According to the results of the augmented Dickey-Fuller test, the logarithmic foreign trade turnover (LNTD) indicator was not stationary at the level, but was stationary in first differences.

Therefore, the ADF test statistic for D(LNTD) was -3.581 . This indicator is less than the critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. However, since the p-value is 0.0013, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Based on the results, it can be concluded that the foreign trade turnover variable is integrated from the first order, i.e.:

LNTD ~ I(1)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.581223	0.0013
Test critical values:		
1% level	-2.708094	
5% level	-1.962813	
10% level	-1.606129	

The CUSUM test is used to check the stability of regression model parameters in the Eviews app. The graph below shows the results of the CUSUM test. The blue line in the graph shows the cumulative sum of the recursive residuals, and the red dotted lines show the critical limits at the 5% significance level. As can be seen, the CUSUM statistic remained within the critical values throughout the entire observation period. This indicates stability of the model parameters over time and the absence of discontinuities.

Figure 2.

The CUSUM statistic (cumulative sum of recursive residuals) remains within critical values at the 5% significance level throughout the entire observation period. It does not exceed the critical lines in any period.

This also indicates that:

- The regression coefficients are stable over time;
- The resulting econometric model is stable and robust.

The Johansen cointegration test was conducted for the period 2008–2024 using the LN_UDM and LNTD variables, accounting for a linear deterministic trend and 1–2 second lags in the first differences.

Johansen Cointegration Test – Trace Statistic

The cointegration test trace statistic was used to determine the presence of a long-run relationship between the variables. The null hypothesis of the test indicates the absence of a

cointegrating relationship between the variables. The trace statistic calculated for the "None" hypothesis was 48.71 (p -value = 0.0000), which is greater than the critical value of 25.87 at the 5% significance level. This result indicates the absence of a cointegrating relationship, and the null hypothesis is rejected.

For the "Not more than 1" hypothesis, the trace statistic was 6.33, with a critical value of 12.52 (p -value = 0.4200). This hypothesis was not rejected. It was determined that only one cointegrating relationship exists between the variables.

As a result, the trace test results confirm the existence of a long-run cointegrating relationship between the LN_UDM and LNTD variables.

The relationship between foreign trade, macroeconomic stability, and economic growth has been widely examined in both theoretical and empirical literature. Early methodological foundations were established in [3], who introduced causality testing in [4], who developed unit root testing procedures, and in [2], who proposed cointegration analysis for identifying long-run equilibrium relationships among time-series variables. These approaches remain essential for analyzing interactions between GDP, trade indicators, money supply, and price dynamics.

Subsequent methodological contributions, including time-series analysis and model-building techniques, expanded the practical application of econometric tools in macroeconomic research. Studies in [5] and [6] emphasize the importance of unit root testing and model specification, while [7] highlights the role of vector autoregression and error-correction models implemented in econometric software.

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Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.917359	48.71175	25.87211	0.0000
At most 1	0.310745	6.326442	12.51798	0.4200

Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p -values

Johansen Cointegration Test – Maximum Eigenvalue Statistic

The maximum eigenvalue statistic of the Johansen cointegration test was used to determine the number of cointegrating relationships between the variables.

The results of the maximum eigenvalue test are consistent with the results of the trace test and indicate the presence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between the LN_UDM and LNTD variables.

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.917359	42.38531	19.38704	0.0000
At most 1	0.310745	6.326442	12.51798	0.4200

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegrating Coefficients (normalized by b'*S11*b=I):

LN_UDM	LNTD	@TREND(2006)
9.915263	-12.87457	0.228698
10.60386	-7.383227	0.056443

Adjustment Coefficients (α)

The adjustment coefficients (α) obtained from the cointegration test show how variables respond to deviations from long-run equilibrium.

According to the results, the adjustment coefficient for D(LNGDP) was 0.145. This coefficient is statistically insignificant (standard error = 0.465). This indicates that GDP responds weakly to deviations from long-run equilibrium in the short run.

Normalized Cointegration Equation (Long-Run Relationship)

Based on the normalized cointegration coefficients, the long-run relationship is expressed as follows:

$$\text{LNNGDP} = 1.298 \cdot \text{LNFT} - 0.023 \cdot \text{TREND LNNGDP} = 1.298 \cdot \text{LN LNFT} - 0.023 \cdot \text{TREND LNNGDP} = 1.298 \cdot \text{LNFT} - 0.023 \cdot \text{TREND}$$

This equation shows that, in the long run, a 1% increase in foreign trade turnover leads to an increase in GDP of approximately 1.3%. The LNTD coefficient is statistically significant and positive. This confirms that foreign trade is a key driver of economic growth.

Unrestricted Adjustment Coefficients (alpha):

D(LNGDP)	0.014630	-0.086837
D(LNFT)	0.184765	-0.095111

1 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood 34.07371

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

LNGDP	LNFT	@TREND(2006)
1.000000	-1.298460	0.023065
	(0.03989)	(0.00242)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(LN_UDM) 0.145057
 (0.46589)

Granger Causality Test Results

A pairwise Granger causality test was used to determine the short-run causal relationship between the variables.

According to the test results:

- The hypothesis " LNFT does not Granger cause LNGDP " is not rejected (p-value = 0.3260);
- The hypothesis " LNGDP does not Granger cause LNFT " is rejected (p-value = 0.0495).

These results indicate that, in the short run, causality runs from GDP to foreign trade. That is, economic growth creates conditions for expanding trade turnover, but foreign trade does not Granger cause GDP in the short run.

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 01/19/26 Time: 21:54

Sample: 2005 2024

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
LNFT does not Granger Cause LNGDP	18	1.22330	0.326
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFT		3.82129	0.049

General Interpretation of the VAR/VECM Model

The results of the VAR/VECM model reflect both long- and short-term dynamics.

The coefficients of the short-term lagged variables in the VAR equations indicate that changes in GDP have a stronger impact on trade turnover. This is consistent with the results of the Granger causality test and indicates that economic growth plays an important role in shaping trade turnover.

VAR Model - Substituted Coefficients:

$$D(LNGDP) = 0.124701219947*(LNGDP(-1) - 2.10947567362*LNFT(-1) + 3.2790245914) + 0.645335138972*D(LNGDP(-1)) - 0.17564881874*D(LNGDP(-2)) - 0.131440315674*D(LNFT(-1)) - 0.0441424499685*D(LNFT(-2)) + 0.0347324765347$$

$$D(LNFT) = 0.472552459788*(LNGDP(-1) - 2.10947567362*LNFT(-1) + 3.2790245914) + 1.5499765452*D(LNGDP(-1)) + 0.0673003502383*D(LNGDP(-2)) - 0.649004659452*D(LNFT(-1)) - 0.313010645978*D(LNFT(-2)) + 0.0497522013248$$

The estimated VECM results indicate the existence of a long-run relationship between LNGDP and LNFT. The error-correction coefficient in the Δ LNGDP equation is 0.1247, implying that approximately 12.5% of the previous period's disequilibrium is corrected in each period, so GDP adjusts slowly toward the long-run equilibrium. In contrast, the coefficient in the Δ LNFT equation is 0.4726, showing that about 47% of deviations are corrected within one period, meaning foreign trade adjusts more rapidly to restore equilibrium.

In the short run, the lagged change of GDP has a strong positive effect on current GDP growth (0.6453), while its second lag has a negative impact (-0.1756). Changes in foreign trade exert a negative short-run effect on GDP (-0.1314 and -0.0441). For the Δ LNFT equation, past GDP changes positively influence foreign trade (1.5500 and 0.0673), whereas its own lags have negative effects (-0.6490 and -0.3130). Overall, the results suggest both short-run dynamics and a stable long-run interaction between economic growth and foreign trade.

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